

Open & Transparent Research Practices

Case Study – Artificial Intelligence

Author: [Simon Kirby](#)

Introduction

Openness and transparency constitute a foundational principle for research integrity, as set out in the UK Concordat to Support Research Integrity. Openness can promote rigour, constructive scrutiny, accountability and can enable others to build on research. However, it can also bring challenges. Critically, what openness and transparency can and should mean varies across disciplines and fields of study. This is one of a series of case studies in a wide range of disciplines that illustrate these differences. The series is intended to enable researchers to see similarities and differences between fields, and to inform those supporting open research through, for example, training, policies or incentives. This case study is from the field of Artificial Intelligence. It is based on a single interview with a researcher, and is therefore illustrative rather than representative.

Background

The field of Artificial Intelligence (AI) is booming, with advances made seemingly weekly in sub-disciplines of machine learning, optimisation, natural language processing, and many more. Applications of the field are found in a wide variety of research areas, from solving protein folding problems, to guiding self-driving cars, from identifying cancerous tumours in medical images, to controlling swarms of autonomous vehicles.

The interviewee is a Research Fellow with a focus on machine learning, computer vision, and explainable AI. Part of their research is focused on the mathematical structures behind AI architectures (such as deep neural networks) and how these can be understood in an explainable way. Alongside this, they are looking at explainable methods and algorithms themselves, and how these can be used to shed light on deep decision-making processes.

In addition, they work on the application of these machine learning methods to interdisciplinary research problems, acting as a technical specialist alongside subject-matter experts. Some of these projects include the identification of early disease indicators in medical data, and also the tracking of invasive species across Europe using novel data sets. Successful outcomes of these projects include publications in peer-reviewed journals, and also successfully gaining grant funding for future research.

Relevance of openness & transparency

Many machine algorithms are not transparent, and the decisions they make not explainable. A hot topic in the field is explainable AI, a research area that aims to explain the inner-workings of often highly accurate, but unexplainable, black-box methods. These highly-complex models are trained on huge volumes of input data, and encode this in model parameters, resulting in a tool that can make decisions on a new piece of input data. Simple decisions can range from whether an image contains a picture of a dog or a cat, what type of advertisement should be displayed to a user, or whether a bank loan should be made.

Explainable AI methods allow researchers to interrogate these complex models, assessing hypotheses about the decision-making process. Whilst these methods might not be able to completely explain this process, they can provide valuable additional views to aid understanding of which features of the input data were important to the decision, in ruling out suspected anomalies, and many more.

Despite the popularity of these black-box models, the research culture feels like one of openness. Similar to the rest of the Computer Science field, it is common for AI researchers to release code alongside their publications, often on GitHub. This is also true for the tech-giants, who release and maintain the state-of-art machine learning libraries, such as TensorFlow and PyTorch. However, it is (understandably) less common for small research groups to create robust packages, and maintain them indefinitely, despite the potential benefits to the wider community.

Finally, publication of data that complex models are trained on is less common, sometimes due to their novelty. However, the set of encoded values (weights) in the trained model are often published as part of the code, or as a release of a pre-trained model itself (i.e. YOLOv5, for object detection).

Pros and cons of openness & transparency

Increased openness and the field of explainable AI have been especially important from an educational point of view, especially with the general public. Being able to explain to younger individuals how advanced technologies, underpinned by complex AI techniques, function is a key step in inspiring the next generation into the field. In addition, uptake and acceptance of these technologies are improved when their decisions are explainable. This can have great benefit, as these technologies can be incredibly powerful.

Within the research community, openness, code publication, and explainability have generally increased the pace of development, all making it fast to pick up, understand and reproduce new ideas, and apply them to new scenarios. When data sets are published, researchers have the opportunity to step into a new application area, and make novel discoveries. However, ethical concerns must be carefully considered when publishing these, especially when dealing with vast portions of medical (and related) data.

When AI software becomes open-source (or at least more open), commercial intellectual property considerations often exist, for both developers and customers. Licensing of cutting-edge libraries and pre-trained models can allow for research and personal use, but are sometimes only available for commercial applications via paid means. Furthermore, it can sometimes be hard for industry to adopt new technologies that are open-source by nature, as there is not necessarily a clear profit-generating route to market. One example from medical research concerns novel, personalised, but un-patentable treatments that are not yet supported by large pharmaceutical companies. This applies to software also: funding and resource for maintaining open-source libraries can be tricky to find in both industry and academia, especially when benefits can appear limited to advertisement and community good.

Wider context & trends

Compared to other fields, the openness of the field of AI is highly apparent. The drive to publish code, and the prolificity and importance of services such as GitHub highlight this. Academics see the value in open-source code, and enjoy the corresponding fast pace of AI research.

Open, transparent peer review is used more frequently than in other fields. When a paper is to be published, comments visible by all are added by a reviewer. These are published via the open journal's website, where the author can publicly respond. This system encourages constructive feedback, keeps authors and reviewers on their toes, and generally feels much more productive, according to the interviewee. In contrast, papers published in mathematics

journals are sent off, and 2 years later, comments come back, before a resubmission. The latter approach feels much less transparent.

It does not seem hugely apparent how the field can become drastically more open. Pressures to be less open with AI research and data are generally from a protective standpoint. Industrial organisations reduce openness to protect intellectual property, and profit-earning potential of creations. Government regulations aim to protect citizens, from data abuses online, such as unfair, automated biases, and physical harm offline, such as the potential of being hit by driverless cars. Finally, additional ethical regulations exist to encourage privacy, accountability, and generally reduce risk to the general public. All of these measures are being discussed at great length in the AI community, and are seen as important.

This work is licensed under a [Creative Commons Attribution-ShareAlike 4.0 International License](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-sa/4.0/).